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Review Article

A Systematic Review of The Association Between Adulthood and Psychological Stress on Menstrual Cycle Irregularity

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this systematic review is to understand correlations between psychological stress and disturbed menstrual cycles in adult women. Irregularities in the menstrual cycle- a condition that affects between 5% and 35.6% of women worldwide- result from influences including age, lifestyle, and psychological status. Stress, for example, disrupts the HPO axis leading to hormonal imbalances, anovulation, and infertility. Other contributory adverse health conditions include unhealthy diets, sleep disorders, sedentary lifestyles, severe physical exercise, and diseases like polycystic ovary syndrome (PCOS), diabetes, and thyroid diseases. Additional agents include medications as well as environmentally-induced toxins. These have been found to point at the importance of considering not just physical factors but psychological also in the management of irregularities within menstruation. Stress reduction, lifestyle changes, and early interventions would be recommended toward restoring reproductive and total wellbeing.

INTRODUCTION

1. Background On Menstrual Cycle Irregularity:

Most of the problems associated with menstruation are largely neglected by primary health care and treated as a minor health concern by the majority of developing countries, India being one of them [1]. Identifying the factors associated with

abnormal menstrual patterns in adolescence could help in their early prevention, which, in turn, could really benefit the reproductive health of adolescents and improve their overall quality of life [2]. There have been increases in the studies that show quite a lot about the association of mental health problems such as stress, anxiety, guilt, all leading to loneliness, life dissatisfaction,

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suicidal thoughts, and substance use in adolescent girls in relation to their menstrual cycle dysfunction [3][4][5]. Greater psychosocial stress among medical students translates into greater instances of menstrual irregularities that showed that increased stress was strongly associated with dysmenorrhea and severe enough premenstrual symptoms to require medication [6]. In this regard, increased mental health problems in early adolescent girls could cause neuroendocrine disruption and chronic activation of the HPA axis during puberty which may lead to multiple types of menstrual irregularities [7]. Previous studies have investigated multiple risk factors associated with menstrual irregularity, such as age at menarche, moderate or vigorous exercise, and obesity. Moreover, other physical risk factors include work-related and psychosocial stress and mental illness as manifested associations between them and factors contributing to the event of these changes. Lifestyle variables like poor diet, lack of exercise, sleep disturbances, substance abuse, travel, and shift work may also cause irregularities in the menstrual cycle. It should also be noted that genetic factors, including hormone regulation genes, reproductive hormone receptor genes, and genes related to polycystic ovary syndrome, and epigenetic factors, interact with environmental and lifestyle factors contributing to the entire process of such irregularities. Some of the medications are also the fore most causative factors for menstrual irregularities.

Prevalence And Consequences On Menstrual Cycle Irregularity:

According to the current literature, the prevalence rates of irregular menstrual cycles range from 5% to 35.6%, depending on the age, nationality, and occupational status of the woman in question [8]. This prevalence has a very extensive range from country to country: 29.7% in Saudi Arabia [9], 35.7% in India [10], 33.3% in Egypt [11], 64.2% in Nepal [12], 14.3% in Korea [13], and 5-15% in

developing countries [14]. A study in Oman found that dysmenorrhea is a very common [94%] but under-treated menstrual disorder among Omani teenage school girls, with only 3% seeking treatment for their severe pains [14]. In Dubai, 94.7% of adolescents reported dysmenorrhea as a significant issue [15]. In a Saudi study, the prevalence of menstrual irregularities during exams was reported to be 48.2% among students of female medical institutions with dysmenorrhea being the most common (70.9%), lengthened cycles (45.6%), and heavy bleeding (41.9%) [16].

Consequences:

Irregular menstruation has wayouth to affect health in other aspects of life and is often considered a marker for women's health itself. Different illness and diseases have also been attributed to it; some of which include metabolic syndrome, coronary heart disease, type 2 diabetes mellitus (DM), and rheumatoid arthritis (RA). Irregular menstruation has much association to pregnancy-related hypertensive disorders, as its strong association as risk for such ends have been demonstrated. Moreover, by this cause, abnormal menstruation before a conception may also predispose the female to adverse effects related to obstetric and neonatal outcomes. These health issues could also impact the availability of work opportunities. [17].

The Purpose And Scope Of The Review:

The aim of this review article is to demonstrate the association between adulthood and psychological stress on menstrual cycle irregularity.

2. Association Between Adulthood And Stress On Menstrual Cycle Irregularity:

During the period of emerging adulthood, great transitions in social roles and crisis levels are usually experienced, and thus their impact on health later in life may be considered. Stress is one of the most important psychological phenomena as regards its end results in mental and physical

health. Psychologically it defines the outcome relations between an individual and an environment that the subject appraises as threatening or exceeding resource capabilities and thereby endangering his or her wellbeing. Prevalence during emerging adulthood young women and men have faced simultaneous challenges: many stressors and demands associated with changes in relationships, work, education, and residence. [18]. Stress is now emerging as an important factor in menstrual cycle irregularities in adulthood. Numerous research studies have suggested the association between psychological stress and adulthood leading to the possible menstrual cycle irregularity. Some of the hormonal changes that occur are probably due to stress-induced disruption of the hypothalamic-pituitary-gonadal (HPG) axes whose activity gets impaired through the hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal (HPA) axis.

1. Adulthood On Menstrual Cycle Irregularity:

As discussed, adulthood is the major cause for menstrual irregularities, mainly due to: Age Related Factors:

1. **Hormonal Decline:** Decrease in estrogen and progesterone levels with age, leading to irregular ovulation and menstruation.
2. **Ovarian Reserve Decline:** Decrease in the number and quality of eggs with an age, leading to reduce fertility and increased risk of menstrual irregularities
3. **Uterine Changes:** Changes in uterine lining and blood flow with age, leading to irregular menstruation and increased risk of bleeding disorder.

Factors Contributing To Menstrual Cycle Irregularities In Adulthood:

- Stress and anxiety
- Sleep quality
- Unhealthy diet and lifestyle
- Medical conditions

- Medications
- Environmental toxins

2. Physiological Stress on Menstrual Cycle Irregularities:

Definition Of Stress: Stress is a complex and multifaced physiological and psychological response to internal or external stimuli that disrupts homeostasis and challenges an individual's ability to cope.

Types Of Stress:

Types of stress depend on the duration, source, or response:

Acute stress: Short-term stress, usually caused by a direct stressor or problem situation. The body goes into fight-or-flight mode, changing temporarily, including increased heart rate due to adrenaline release.

Chronic stress: Present when the stress is for a protracted period. Prolonged exposure to chronic stress cumulatively could bring about physiological and psychological consequences, thus increasing susceptibility to health problems like cardiovascular disease, anxiety, and depression.

Episodic acute stress: The individual seems to go through multiple episodes of acute stress. Such a behavior could lead to defining a person as being disorganized or unorganized and under constant sense of deadline, obligation, or conflict. This cycle perpetuates health problems and deterioration of normal life functioning.

Traumatic Stress: This comes from accident-trauma events. Natural disasters, accidents, or violence are some examples of events that can create trauma so great that a person's capacity to withstand it cannot process everything that occurs. This leads to symptoms of posttraumatic stress disorder (PTSD) such as having intrusive memories, avoidance behavior, and hyperarousal.

Stress arising from the environment: These types of stressors could emanate from adverse or stressful external conditions such as noise,

pollution, overcrowding, and insecure living conditions. Such stressors may damage the mental and physical health of the people and lead to discomfort or uneasiness.

Psychological Stress: This type outcome from cognitive or emotional impact such as perceived threats, worries, or negative thoughts. Typical stressors include those found in work pressures, academic expectations, social comparisons, or self-imposing demands. Symptoms may present themselves in anxiety, rumination, or perfectionism.

Physiological stress: Physiological stress may be defined as that response of the body by way of disorganization of the normally established homeostasis condition as a consequence of internal or external stressors. Diseases, injuries, lack of sleep, or lack of nutrition may trigger physiological stress pathways and jeopardize health and well-being [19].

Mechanism Of Stress Effect On Menstrual Cycle Irregularity:

Physiological stress, because it affects the hypothalamic-pituitary-ovarian axis, disrupts the menstrual cycle. The HPG axis regulates a complex array of behaviors and physiology in conjunction with the successful reproduction, both in terms of sexual functioning and fertility, as well as hormones. Within the HPG axis, activity is triggered by the hypothalamic secretion of the gonadotropin-releasing hormone (GnRH) and with downstream effects on two gonadotropins, luteinizing hormone (LH) and follicle-stimulating hormone (FSH), both produced in the anterior pituitary gland. In females, FSH promotes the growth and maturation of ovarian follicles while LH induces ovulation and stimulates the synthesis and release of steroid sex hormones from gonads/ovaries, that is, estradiol (E2) and progesterone. The sex hormones produced by the ovaries feedback to the hypothalamus and pituitary through action on kisspeptin affecting production

of GnRH, FSH, and LH. This feedback system, inhibitory-stimulatory types of combined relationships between hormones, closely regulates and keeps balanced hormone levels for optimal reproductive functioning and cyclical release of hormones [20]. Stress can unbalance the equilibrium of the reproductive axis due to inhibition of gonadotropin-releasing hormone secretion from the hypothalamus, which, in turn, reduces luteinizing hormone and follicle-stimulating hormone release from the pituitary gland. All of this results in disrupted ovarian functioning in women. stress may bring about menstrual irregularities, anovulation, and infertility among female patients, along with loss of sexual interest. Hormonal changes due to stress and disruption in reproductive functions can also lead to other conditions like polycystic ovary syndrome.

1. Life Style Factors Intensify The Menstrual Cycle Irregularity:

✚ **Eating Disorder:** The most common eating disorders which can be seen among women in their puberty and early adult life are also the causative factors for menstruation disorders like amenorrhea or irregular menses. Anorexia nervosa is characterized by girls with very low body weight who mostly eat very little and bulimia nervosa is a compensatory behavior that is seen in women having a normal weight and binge eats but purges later on. Rapid loss of body weight, low body weight, overweight and eating behaviors of the individual and subsequent problems associated with deficiency of nutrients intake or lifestyle can be enumerated in terms of menstrual disorder [22].

✚ **Obesity:** Child and adolescent obesity have been shown to carry numerous adverse health effects including insulin resistance and type 2 diabetes mellitus, hypertension, hyperlipidemia, fatty liver disease not caused by alcohol, sleep apnea that obstructs, gallbladder disease, pseudotumor cerebri,

slipped capital femoral epiphysis, and Blount disease, depression, and eating disorders. Among adolescent females, these neuroendocrine effects of obesity show themselves in precocious puberty and earlier-than-expected menarche; hyperandrogenism creates irregularities or omissions in the menstrual cycle, abnormal bleeding from the uterus, polycystic ovary syndrome, and greater prevalence of dysmenorrhea and premenstrual disorders [23].

✚ **Physical Activity And A Sedentary Lifestyle:**

The reproductive hormones, ovulation, and fertility were all influenced by physical activity. The women who lived sedentary are likely to experience noticeable emotional and physical menstrual symptoms. On the contrary, moderate physical activity tended to increase the menstrual cycle controlled by FSH pulses, which delayed ovulation and lengthened the follicular phase, while extreme exercise caused changes in the luteal phase that resulted in oligomenorrhea and amenorrhea. Sedentary women will experience amenorrhea at the initial stage of exercise. Physical activity is usually detrimental to the menstrual cycle, particularly still being during the time of dysmenorrhea. Regular low-intensity physical exercises, on the other hand, reduce dysmenorrhea and decrease the need for extra medication in young females with dysmenorrhea. Physical and psychological well-being would culminate in general enhancement [24] for increased endorphin levels and stabilization of hormonal levels and their effects on the hypothalamic-pituitary axes, as well as improved oxygen supply to muscles.

✚ **Diet:** Menstrual health forms one of the significant parts of women health and therefore menstrual characteristics. Busy and modern lifestyle has changed the eating habits of today's. One side has an increasing consumption of fast

food, caffeine, alcohol, and other beverages. On the other hand, the increased incidence of menstrual problems and reproductive issues is increasing. These functions are reproductive and in harmony with their hormonal balance, which sometimes relies on the food and food habits of that person. Eating disorders are common features of menstrual disorder and they multifaceted and result from the complex interplay of many factors including weight loss, decreased body fat, hypo leptinemia, abnormal eating attitudes, behavior's, exercise, and psychological stressors [25].

✚ **Sleep Disturbances:** Sleep is indispensable to effective performance in various daily tasks for the adolescents, mostly for enhancing the sleep pattern and sleep quality achievement in academic success and holistic quality of life. Sleep deprivation ends up with malfunctions during the day, psychological and behavioral issues, as well as physical ailments like obesity. Baker and Driver said that circadian disruption, such as sleep and awake disorders, might have something to do with disruption in the menstrual cycle- this fact corresponds to about one-third of adolescents experience sleep disturbance, and only 1 in 10 adolescents are estimated to sleep more than 8 h, as recommended by the National Sleep Foundation. According to the research, these poor sleep patterns in adolescents seem to correlate with exposure to various types of screen light, which include watching TV and playing computer games, having some after-school jobs, and also academic pressure. This kind of activity may interfere with the circadian rhythm, which has effects on the menstrual cycle of female adolescents. Nevertheless, the relationship between sleep duration and menstrual cycle regularity has barely been studied in the adolescent population [26].

✚ Psychological Factors Involved In Menstrual Cycle Irregularity:

Notably, about 20% of adolescents experience depressive symptoms and female adolescents are more likely to experience depressive symptoms than are male adolescents [27]. The result of strong depression is observed due to early perimenopause and menopause. The strongest association was obtained among women attaining menopause naturally before the age of 40 years. Promotional

CRH levels during depression cause inhibition of the hypothalamic- pituitary-gonadal (HPG) axis and increased cortisol levels, which further inhibit the action of gonadotropin-releasing hormone (GnRH) neurons, gonadotropins, and gonads leading to changes in luteinizing hormone (LH) amplitude and follicle-stimulating hormone (FSH) level along with LH pulse frequency noted in patients with depression [28].

Figure: 1 Depression Affecting Reproductive Hormones

Anxiety typically arises in response to stressful events and can affect an individual’s quality of life [29]. An increase of 1 unit in the anxiety score increased the risk of menstrual irregularities by 1.081 times [30]. Anxiety causes systemic changes in the body, especially in the nervous system. Anxiety triggers the release of the hormone cortisol where the hormone cortisol suppresses the hypothalamus and interferes with the work and function of the hypothalamus, one of which is to secrete the menstrual hormones follicle stimulating hormone (FSH) and luteinizing

hormone (LH). Changes in prolactin or endogenous opiates occur which affect the basal cortisol elevation is a disturbance in the hormones LH and FSH, it will affect the production of estrogen and progesterone so that it will cause menstrual cycle irregularities [31].

7. Disease Conditions Alters The Menstrual Cycle Irregularity:

The hormonal changes and results of menstrual disturbances that were observed in various endocrine disorders.

Table: 1 Disease Conditions Alters The Menstrual Cycle Irregularity

Type Of Disorders/Ref	Possible Mechanism	Type Of Menstrual Cycle Disturbances
1.PCOS [32][33]	Increased LH and androgen secretion, prolonged exposure to estrogen	Long and irregular menstrual cycles secondary amenorrhea and oligomenorrhea
2.DIABETES [34][35]	Increased LH and FH ratio and androgens and decreased gonadotrophin levels, hyperinsulinemia.	Oligomenorrhea, long cycles, long and heavy menstruation

3.HYPERPROLACTINEMIA [36][37]	Inhibition of LH, GNRH, and may be FSH	Amenorrhea, bleeding between cycles, oligomenorrhea, polymenorrhea and hypermenorrhea
4.HYPER THYROIDISM [38][39]	Decreased SHBG, estradiol (E2), testosterone levels.	Irregular menses, heavy bleeding, oligomenorrhea, amenorrhea, breakthrough bleeding
5.THYROTOXICOSIS [39]	Increased estradiol, testosterone levels and androgen conversion to estrone.	Oligomenorrhea, amenorrhea
6.CUSHING'S SYNDROME [40][41]	Ovarian damage, androgens, hypercortisolism.	Amenorrhea, oligomenorrhea, polymenorrhea

Among others, here are some of the neurological conditions that affect the proper menstrual cycle: epilepsy, multiple sclerosis, and parkinsonism.

- COVID 19: The scientists have investigated the relationship between COVID and the menstrual cycle and concluded that infection with the coronavirus could lead to very short-term altered menstrual cycles. The menstrual irregularities related to COVID have been explained by several potential mechanisms:
- Evidence suggests that that coronavirus infection can be stressful. This stress may affect production of ovulatory hormones, leading to menstrual changes [42].
- The coronavirus binds to the angiotensin-converting enzyme-2 receptor [ACE-2]. It enters cells and extends invasion everywhere throughout the bodies including the ovaries and endometrium (the inner lining of the uterus)—the area that thickens each month in preparation for an embryo. If that embryo is not implanted there, this inner lining sheds and exits the body via the vaginal canal. In case this virus binds at ACE-2 receptors in the ovaries and the endometrium, the virus may directly damage these structures and produce menstrual irregularities [42].

8. Medications Contributes To Menstrual Cycle Irregularity:

So many medicines include hormonal contraceptives, antidepressants, antipsychotics, chemotherapeutics, antiepileptics, and immunosuppressants, which would cause most women to be thus affected with menstrual disturbance by hormonal imbalance, neurological changes, and suppression of the pituitary gland in their systems.

9. Genetic Factors Involved In Menstrual Cycle Irregularity:

Puberty is not solely a process determined by external factors at the environment level but also by the internal genetic and familial variables. Genetic differences and diversity, according to a longitudinal study conducted by Tu and colleagues, present a very significant stimulating factor in the development of puberty stages [43]. The age of menarche is greatly influenced by several genes, such as those of the estrogen-metabolizing type as well as CCR3 genes and CYP17 (18-20). Maternal age is believed to be the most important factor affecting both age at menarche for adolescents and age at which the regulation of the menstrual cycle begins [44, 45]. It has been reported in two large studies that 23 to 57% of differences in the age of menarche can be

attributed to genetic and familial causes [46, 47]. High levels of androgens, as mentioned earlier, modulate menstrual cycle regulation in adolescents. There has been some recent interest in genetic factors in PCOS development that affect the regulation of the menstrual cycle. Current molecular genetic studies show that genes involved in androgen regulation may be implicated in the development of hyperandrogenism [48]. Indications of genetic defects include permutations of fragile X, X chromosome abnormalities, and point mutations in the enzyme galactose-1-phosphate uridyl transferase (GALT) galactosemia, which may interfere with the menstrual cycle. The complicated surge and variations in different reproductive hormones modify the menstrual cycle [49]. Some genetic factors associated with autoimmune disorders among these 3 genetic factors associated with menstrual cycle irregularities are:

Lupus

Rheumatoid arthritis

Hashimoto's thyroiditis.

METHODS:

On 28th Nov 2024, a systematic database search of PUBMED, SCIENCE DIRECT, MDPI, NCBI, SCIENCE DIRECT.COM and BENTHAM DIRECT.COM was done with the focus on studies exploring the connection between psychological stress and adulthood on menstrual cycle irregularities. Abstract, full text screening, and data extraction was done by three independent investigators. Findings are summarized with the help of Descriptive statistics.

DISCUSSION:

The current survey seems to be the first thorough systematic assessment of the evidence available on psychological stress in adulthood and its relationship with menstrual cycle irregularity. We reviewed vast literature and extracted data from various articles.

Recommendations:

1. Add mental health resources: Healthcare professionals must also start considering mental health resources in menstrual cycle irregularities treatment plans.

2. Teach Stress Reduction Techniques: Women who experience irregularities in their menstrual cycle should be taught stress reduction including methods such as mediation, yoga, or deep breathing exercises.

3. Promote lifestyle changes: Support lifestyle changes like regular activity, healthy eating, and proper sleep in order to alleviate stress with possible added benefits to regularity of menstrual cycles.

Prioritize early treatment: The prompt treatment and management of irregular menstrual cycles may prevent long-term complications and improve life quality.

By understanding the complexities, health professionals will better be able to address the needs of women who are struggling with these challenges.

CONCLUSION:

The following is the revised conclusion concerning psychology in adulthood and psychological stress regarding irregularities in the menstrual cycles. Most women tend to face such irregularities during their adult periods. Almost all women experience their changes from adolescence to adulthood, and most of this change almost everything in their lives: their bodies, moods, and even the people they associate with. Very psychological stress on the other hand causes menstrual irregularities during adulthood. Stress is prolonged; it disrupts the Hypothalamic-Pituitary-Gonadal (HPG) axis disturbance, after which there is hormone and menstrual irregularities. It defines the relationship between adulthood and psychologic distress on menstrual irregularities and typically crucial within this context. Transitions into adulthood may cause psychological stress and disrupt the regular pattern

of the menstrual cycle. For example, some cycle irregularities may also contribute to psychological distress, leading to the repetition such a cycle. Understanding the dynamic interplay of adulthood, psychological stress, and the incoherence of the menstrual cycle is crucial to devising effective preventive and intervention strategies. Healthcare professionals must consider both psychological and emotional dimensions of the irregularity in the menstrual cycle when diagnosing it or providing treatment to women affected by it.

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